

REORIENTATION OF SiC WHISKERS IN ALUMINUM AT DIFFERENT STAGES
OF EXTRUSION

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ABSTRACT

Silicon carbide whisker-reinforced aluminum metal-matrix composites exhibit technologically attractive properties such as fracture toughness, strength, wear resistance, controlled thermal expansion and good fatigue resistance. Since these properties are fiber orientation dependent, shaping by plastic deformation produces textures of whiskers that result in anisotropic regions with varying mechanical and physical characteristics. To optimize the design and the properties of deformation-processed composites, it is desirable to understand the relationship between whisker orientation distribution and the forming mode. This study investigated the orientation distribution of SiC_w in a hot-pressed 2024 aluminum alloy matrix at various positions in the billet, die and extrudate.

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The hot-pressed composite used in this study was clad with unreinforced 2024 aluminum alloy, then extruded at room temperature to diameter reduction ratios of 2.4 and 3.0. To evaluate the effect of matrix flow on the redistribution of whisker orientation during the extrusion process, scanning electron photomicrographs taken at various positions on the cross-section progressing along extrusion streamlines were analyzed. Progressive changes of whisker orientation during the deformation process were measured by a stereographic method.

Experimental results indicate that the extrusion process attained a whisker distribution highly oriented in the extrusion direction. It is observed that a more reduced extrudate shows more whiskers aligned in the extrusion direction. Near the die surface, the SiC whiskers are at smaller angles with the extrusion direction than those near the center of the extruded rod. To explain the whisker reorientations, a metal flow-pattern model is developed. In this model, the assumption of a kinematically-admissible spherical velocity field in the extrusion die is adopted. The reoriented whisker distribution based on the velocity gradient is predicted and compared with experimental results.

KEYWORDS: short fiber composite, silicon carbide, aluminum, extrusion, angular distributions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Metals reinforced with particles, short fibers or whiskers are useful, not only because of mechanical and physical property improvements, but also because these materials can be shaped in the solid state by cold or hot

working processes. Forming, however, alters the initial distributions of particles, especially those having one dimension greater than the other two. Short fibers and whiskers are representative of rod-shaped geometries useful in composites. Their shape is usually defined by the length/diameter ratio, L/D. To better understand the process of redistribution, an axially symmetric deformation process, extrusion through a conical converging die, is used in experiments with whisker reinforced composites. A model which describes this shaping process for a homogeneous metal has been presented in detail by Avitzur¹. This analysis is extended to consider short fibers or whiskers in a ductile metal matrix. The materials employed for corresponding experiment are SiC_w whiskers with an L/D about 20 in a 2024 aluminum matrix. The 20 volume percent powdered mixture, supplied by ARCO Chemical Company², was hot pressed in a vacuum at 500°C into compacts 25 mm in diameter and 51 mm long. The compact was cut into several cylinders 7.94 mm (0.3125 in) in diameter by electric discharge machining. To facilitate room temperature extrusion, each cylinder was clad with a 2024 aluminum tube of 9.525 mm (0.375 in) outside diameter. One pass extrusions were carried out through a 45° conical die with Synthelube® lubricant at a ram speed of about 18 mm/s. Two degrees of reduction were investigated: initial/extruded diameters (extrusion reduction ratio), (1) 3.0, and (2) 2.4.

During reduction in the die, whiskers encounter a material flow gradient in a deforming ductile matrix. The resulting arrangements of whiskers depend upon initial whisker

distribution, extrusion reduction ratio (ER), die shape and die angle. In the case of composites with rigid, discrete reinforcements in a pliant medium, strain at the interface is dependant on the strength of adhesion and the plasticity of the matrix. Local strain near the interface can be much greater than the average strain of the composite, and in some cases the phases may part, forming voids adjacent to the reinforcing phase as the solid flows through the die.³ For a given initial orientation distribution of the whiskers or short fibers, reshaping will produce a different orientation distribution in the product.

The evolution of whisker reorientation was observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) after sectioning and etching away part of the aluminum matrix⁴ at the midplane of the billet and measuring the angular distributions of whiskers by a stereographic technique. Sampling points were selected along lines of flow so that areas in the billet at different initial distances from the centerline could be examined at several stages of the shaping operation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 1 indicates the approximate positions of areas viewed by SEM. The angular distribution of whiskers in the unextruded portion of the specimen was created by the hot-pressing operation in which a random distribution of the blended metal powder and the SiC_w was compacted from the loose state to approximately full density. This distribution is common for positions S_{i1} . On the other hand, all other positions on the plastically deformed composite after it entered the die have different angular distributions. A

stereographic pair of photomicrographs of an area investigated is shown in Figure 2. Angles from 0° to 90° between clearly observed whiskers and the extrusion axis was measured, however, it is more descriptive of the process to consider angles between 0° to 180° from the extrusion

Figure 1: SEM sample locations; S_{ij} .

Figure 2: Stereographic SEM pair from which whisker orientations were determined.

direction. As will be explained when the model is presented, the resulting distribution has transverse radial symmetry, but the magnitude of rotation of each whisker depends on its original orientation with respect to the extrusion direction and its distance from the center line. Because of these factors, longitudinal symmetry does not develop.

Nevertheless, the 0° to 90° range reported will be compared

Figure 3: Angular distributions at positions S_{ij} for $RA = 2.4$ and $RA = 3.0$.

with the model. Figure 3 is the results for ER 2.4 and 3.0.

3. MODEL

Avitzler divided extrusion of a cylindrical rod into three zones: zone I is the unextruded portion of the rod, and zone III is the extrudate down stream of the converging region. See Figure 4. The velocity in zone I, v_o , and in zone III, v_f , are constant, and are related by

$$v_o = v_f \left[\frac{R_f}{R_o} \right]^2 \quad (1)$$

The flows in each of these zones are uniform. In the die, however,

$$v = \frac{-v_f r_f^2 \cos \theta}{r^2} \quad (2)$$

Figure 4: Avitzur's model applied to an oriented whisker.

velocity is directed

toward the apex of cone, O , and its magnitude depends on the position in zone II defined by the angle θ , where θ is the angle between the ray extending from the apex and r is the distance from O . Zone II, the region of plastic deformation, is bounded by two spherical surfaces Γ_1 and Γ_2 of radii r_f and r_o , respectively. The included angle of the cone is 2α , where α is the die angle.

The model is based on the relative magnitudes of the flow velocities at the ends of a whisker, and δ , the angle which the whisker makes with respect to the extrusion direction. The value of δ can be determined at any position in each of the three zones. In zones I and II, the orientation of the whisker remains the same since there is no velocity gradient; in zone II, the flow rate is the greatest at the extrusion axis, and therefore, the whisker will change orientation -- except in situations when it enters the die parallel to the axis, or when it is perpendicular to the axis with its midpoint on the extrusion axis. Angle δ defined as 0° in the extrusion direction and increases clockwise to 180° from this direction. Angles from 180° to 360° are not unique because of

the symmetry of the whisker. Although this model is most accurate when applied to a fiber which has the same elasticity and plasticity of the matrix, it is a reasonable approximation for a rigid whisker in a maluable matrix. The assumptions in this model do not consider bending nor the fact that longitudinal strain of the whisker is very small with respect to the highly deformed matrix in the die.

Figure 5: Calculated distributions from model at the same locations the experimental observations were made.

If the model is applied to a composite with a starting whisker distribution similar to the obtained in the hot pressed billets⁵, calculations of the altered distributions can be determined for the same locations as measure in the experiments. Figure 5 is a comparison of the predicted distributions from the model.

4. DISCUSSION

Although there is not a perfect fit between the data and the angular distributions derived from the model, agreement is generally good. Experimental methods of determining short fiber distribution are all difficult; each has some disadvantages. For example in the method used, wherein the surface is polished and etched, there is a greater possibility of the whiskers parallel to the axis and nearly parallel to the surface being lost. This loss will bias the measured distribution, giving a lesser frequency at small angles. Differences in the distributions in Figures 3 and 5 can be partially attributed to this effect. Although many whiskers were measured, larger populations would certainly improve the fit, and similar measurements on transverse cross sections would produce more reliable results for small fiber angles.

5. CONCLUSIONS

An elementary model for fiber reorientation based upon Avitzur's upper bound analysis of axisymmetric extrusion agrees, in general, with experimental data for whisker reinforced aluminum. Other models which might consider near-rigid reinforcement in a ductile matrix and relative elastic and plastic strains could produce more realistic descriptions of the micro-mechanics of the process.

6. REFERENCES

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7. BIOGRAPHY

Irwin G. Greenfield is an Unidel Professor of Materials Science and Mechanical Engineering. His major research interests concern effects of surfaces and interfaces on physical and mechanical properties of materials. At present, his efforts involve fabrication, orientation effects and physical properties of metal matrix composites reinforced with short fibers.

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Nancy J-J. Fang is presently a graduate student attending the University of Pennsylvania. She obtained her undergraduate and Masters degrees from the University of Delaware. The experimental work reported herein, is based on her award winning senior project. Her Masters thesis on ceramic material composites was supervised by Professor T-W. Chou.

